

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14314228

Influence Of Financing Decision On The Market Value Of Listed Consumer Goods Companies In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of financing decision on the market value of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study examined the influence of financing decision variables like short term debt and long -term debt on market value. Purposive sampling technique was used to determine the sample size of 15 out of study's population of 21 listed consumer goods companies. Secondary data were sourced from Annual Reports and Account of sampled companies from 2013 to 2022. The study used Descriptive Statistics, correlation analysis and panel data regression methods. The results revealed that there long -term debt had positive and significant effect on market value (t-val= 3.3165, $p<0.05$), implies that long-term debt allows companies to leverage their capital structure, potentially increasing returns on equity. In addition, short term debt had positive and significant effect on market value (t-val= 2.0097, $p<0.05$), implies that short-term debt can help companies manage their liquidity needs effectively by providing quick access to cash for operational expenditures or to cover temporary cash shortfalls. On the side of control variable, return on assets had positive and significant effect on market value (t-val= 4.9576, $p<0.05$). The study concluded that the financing decision had positive and statistical significant impact on market value of selected consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study recommended that companies must carefully manage their short-term debt strategies to optimize the balance between accessibility to funds and maintaining investor confidence to sustain or enhance their market value.

Keywords: Financing decision, market value, short term debt, long -term debt, tobins q

INTRODUCTION

The market value of a firm is a crucial indicator that reflects investors' perceptions of its performance and plays a vital role in ensuring long-term growth and sustainability. It embodies the conditions a company strives to attain, fostering public trust in its operations. The activities of investors concerning stock prices are intricately tied to this market value (Darmawan et al., 2019). Ultimately, a firm's foremost goal is to boost its market value, which directly correlates with the wealth of its owners or stockholders, reinforcing the importance of strategic decision-making in achieving corporate success. In comparison to the concept of market value, firm value is a concept that demonstrates the worth of the firm, as well as financial debts (Syamsudin et al., 2017). It is a company's value based on the total market value of its outstanding shares, or market capitalization. Tobins Q, which indicates management performance in managing firm assets, is one of the options used to estimate business value (Sudiyatno & Puspitasari, 2010). The worth of a

company has become a crucial criterion for investors when deciding whether to invest or not in the search of a higher return on their investment. This explains the reason while firm value is central to the growth and survival of a firms and why the issue of firm value has continued to attract attention in corporate finance and accounting literature. Given its role on the firms going concern, identifying factors that influence the market value of the firm becomes imperative. Samuel, Ebenezer and Xicang (2012) shared that the capital structure decision of a firm should be examined from the point of its impact on the value of the firm. He further states that if capital structure decision can affect a firm's value, then firms would like to have a capital structure which maximizes their value. The aim of a firm should centre therefore on the maximization of its value through capital structure decisions (Samuel et al. 2012). Finance is so vital and serves as an instant cause for companies not commencing or progressing. Capital structure serves as one of the important variables considered by firms when considering financial performance.

The debt financing is often represented by the capital structure which describes how much equity a company owns comes from debts to creditors. In addition to the debt to equity ratio, capital structure is also proxy with long term debt ratio and short term ratio in literature. The greater the debt the company has, the greater the risk it must bear. The higher the cost that must be incurred by the company to pay off these debts.

The listed consumer companies in Nigeria do find it difficult to make a profit; this does affect their performance which may be attributed to inadequate finance or where the finance is available at a cost too expensive (Akintoye, 2016; Ajibola, Wisdom & Qudus , 2018). The problem of financing decision, therefore, arises from determining the quantum of each source of finance that will yield optimum return with little risks (Akintoye, 2016; Dada & Ghazali, 2016). In Nigeria, one of the fundamental causes of corporate distress points to the fact that inadequate capital, mismatch in finance and inappropriate capital mix characterize the Nigeria firms (Oboh, Isa & Adekoya 2012) .Generally, firms are faced with a complex challenges list of options when deciding on their choice of financing decision. Most firms have to choose either to finance their investments with retained earnings, new equity issues, or through debt. However, it has been observed that the Nigerian firms most often use equity rather than debt in financing projects as compared to firms in the developed nations (Adeyemi & Oboh, 2011). There has been a limited number of studies in Nigeria that have examined the firm's choice of financial decisions and its market value, but few researchers gave different view and results on firm's choice of capital structure which include: Oboh, Isa & Adekoya (2012) studied the corporate capital structure and corporate market value in Nigeria. Lawal (2014) investigated the capital structure and the value of the firm in Nigerian banking industry. Other research works focused on the capital structure and financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria and /or in other countries include, Ajibola, Wisdom & Qudus (2018); Oladunjoye, et al., (2021), Ifada et al. (2019), Chaleeda et al. (2019) and Getahun (2016). However, the review of previous empirical literature revealed a lack of established on the influence of financing decision on the market value of listed consumer companies in south-west geo-political zone in Nigeria over the period of 2013-2022. Few researchers used dependent variable of tobins q proxy market value and independent variables of short term debt and long term debt measure financing decision for period of 2013-2022. Few of researchers focused on consumer-goods companies for a period till 2018 which indicates the existence of a research gap. In view of the above, it is essential to comprehend how organization's financing method impact their market value. Therefore, the crucial theme of this research is to evaluate the influence of financing decision on the market value of listed consumer goods companies in southwest geopolitical zone in Nigeria. To achieve the research objective of this study, the following research questions were raised. What is the influence of financing decision (total equity, short term debt and long term debt) on market value of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria? The broad objective of this study is investigate the influence of financing decision (short term debt and long term debt) on market value of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria: The study will be of significant to the shareholders and varying stakeholders, including senior management, managers and policy makers will find of this study useful so as to aid them for an effective and efficient financing decision of firms in

Nigeria. Consultants and financial analysts will find the study helpful in their financial and advisory services to failing and distressed companies

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Financing Decisions

Financing decision is the second important function to be performed by the financial manager. Broadly, financial manager must decide when, where from and how to acquire funds to meet the firm's investment needs. The central issue before financial manager is to determine the appropriate proportion of equity and debt. The mix of debt and equity is known as the firm's capital structure. The financial manager must strive to obtain the best financing mix or the optimum capital structure for the firm (Pandey, 2005). The firm's capital structure is considered optimum when the market value of shares is maximized

In the absence of debt, the shareholders' return is equal to the firm's return. The use of debt affects the return and risk of shareholders; it may increase the return on equity funds, but it always increases risk as well. The change in the shareholders' return caused by the change in the profits is called the financial leverage. A proper balance will have to be struck between return and risk. When the shareholders' return is maximized with given risk, the market value per share will be maximized and the firm's capital structure would be considered optimum (Pandey, 2005). Once the financial manager is able to determine the best combination of debt and equity, he or she must raise the appropriate amount through the best available sources. In practice, a firm considers many other factors such as control, flexibility, loan covenants, legal aspects etc. in deciding its capital structure.

A financing decision is a pivot of achieving financial objectives organization and this decision arises as a result of previous, current and future performance of an organization. Therefore, financing decision (capital structure) relates to the raising of finance from various sources depending on the type of source, period of financing, cost of financing and the re-turns. When companies need to raise money, they can invite investors to put up cash in exchange for shares of future profits, or it can promise to pay back the investor's cash plus a fixed rate of interest. The investors in this case are referred to as equity investors, who contribute equity financing. In the second case, the investors are lenders, that is, debt investors, who one day must be repaid. Corporate financing decision deal with amount of capital that is required for a firm to operate and the best mix of capital structure for the firm (Pike & Neale, 2009). To maximize the firm value, all the rational firms will pursue the lowest cost of capital and the optimal capital structure. Firms that have a pertinent blend of debt and equity will benefit the firm in the long run. The build-up of an optimal debt-equity mixture will reduce the cost of capital, and increase the net economic returns and consequently raise the firm's value (Chaleeda, Islam, Ahmad & Ghazalat, 2019). Companies fund their investment projects using internal and external funds. Internal financing is whereby companies use non-cash expenses and retained earnings, and external financing refers to the proceeds from new equity and debt issuance. In a capital market world, internal and external funds are not perfect substitutes, and thus dividends, financing, and investment decisions are related (Simmons-Süer, 2016). Moreover, firms prefer to use internal funds to finance additional investments rather than issuing new securities because when there are capital market imperfections, internal funds are cheaper sources of financing

Equity Capital This involves the capability to source external and also issue out equity shares right certified by a share certificate. The equity shareholders own part of the firm. At financial period ending, companies issue dividend to shareholders from the profit made by the firm (Efobi, 2008) and (Ajibola, et al., 2018). Equity unlike long term debt include paid up capital share-premium, reserves and surplus or retained earnings. Paid-up capital is the amount of money a company has received from shareholders in exchange for shares of stock. He also states that paid up capital is when a company sells its shares on the primary market directly to investors, usually through an initial public offering (IPO) (Chen, Jiang, & Lin, 2014). Reserves may be voluntarily created by directors or statutorily required by law. Share premium is the excess amount derived from the issue of shares at a price that is above its par value (Samual, Ebenzer

& Xicang 2012). And lastly, retain earnings are profit plough back in to a company in order to create more resources for operations and invariably increase in the market value.

Debt Capital

Debt maturity choice is another aspect of capital structure which is proven to impact market value. This is because the wrong choice of debt maturity might expose firms to interest rate fluctuations and potential rollover difficulties and consequently, make it difficult for firms to pursue valuable growth opportunities. (Chaleeda, Islam, Ahmad & Ghazalat, 2019).

From one perspective, shorter maturity debt may enhance market value as shorter maturity debt is beneficial because it alleviates the underinvestment and asset substitution problems. However, firms with outstanding debt may have incentives to reject projects that have positive net present value if the benefit from accepting the project accrues to the bondholders without also increasing shareholders' wealth. Ihenetu, et al., (2016) posit that debt capital is the long span obligation an entity applies in funding its investment activities which is accompanied with a long repayment period. The cost of debt in an entity's capital structure hinge on the state of its financial position (Ajibola, et al., 2018)

Long-term debt to total equity is a ratio that gauges how much long-term debt bears in on a company's capital structure (long-term financing). The long-term debt-to- total equity ratio is a measure of a company's capacity to satisfy its financial obligations. Because this ratio is computed annually, a decrease in the ratio indicates that the business is doing well and is less reliant on debt to meet its demands (Odunsanya et al., 2018). The more long-term debt a firm has, the more crucial it is for it to generate positive revenue and consistent cash flow. Checking the debt structure and determining debt capacity is extremely beneficial to management (Akinsulire, 2014). Long-term debt is debt that is due for repayment in more than a year and is not included in the balance sheet's current liabilities calculation. Mortgages and long-term leases are included, but not basic trading obligations (Akinyomi and Olagunju 2013). Because the corporation must satisfy principle and interest commitments, a high ratio usually indicates a higher level of business risk. Potential creditors are hesitant to lend money to a company that is heavily in debt. The size of the debt, however, is determined by the sort of business.

Market Value

Market value is the worth of a company based on the total value of its outstanding shares in the market or its market capitalization. It is the perception of the investor to the success of a company. It is reflected in the share price of the company. The increase of the share price shows the trust of the investors to the company. They are willing to pay more with aiming for a higher return. The firm value is the total assets owned. It consists of the market value of share and liabilities (Ifada, Faisal, Ghazali, & Udin , 2019) . The high stock price can provide a good signal to attract investors to determine investment decisions. The market value in this study uses proxies of tobins q

Return on Assets (ROA): Return on assets is a measure of performance widely used in corporate governance literature for accounting based measures. Gichuhi (2016) defined ROA as a function of how profitable a firm is in totality of its entire assets. It shows the efficacy of the board and executives in terms of deploying all the assets of the firm to its maximum use and proper utilization. It is a measure which assesses the effectiveness of assets deployed and shows investors the earnings the company has realized from its investment in capital assets. The return on assets shows the shareholders how much the managers are committing the fund of the firm into net income.

Theoretical Framework

This study considered pecking order theory, because when choosing which funds to use in financing, firms first use to consider their internal sources of funds, or retained earnings, then debt, and lastly equity. Using retained earnings involves lower funding costs and shorter processing times compared to debt funding, yet equity funding involves yet higher funding costs and even longer processing times. Therefore, debt financing positively affects firm value in term of market share price, net asset per share,

market capitalization. Firms with more profit and liquidity have more retained earnings and do not need external funding. Firms involved in high-risk ventures should not need more debt as more debt means even more financial risk. However, growth opportunities and noncurrent assets positively affect liability. The retained earnings of high growth firms might not match their capital requirements, so they add more debt. Moreover, tangible assets can be used as security when firms require debt funding.

Empirical Review

Oladunjoye, et al., (2021) studied debt equity and share price performance of manufacturing companies' listed in Nigeria using sample size of fifteen (15) listed manufacturing firms between 2010 and 2019. The Panel regression model was used. Results revealed that the total debt to equity ratio is negative and significant influence on performance of share price return on assets is also seen to be positive and significantly influence the performance of share price of listed manufacturing firm in Nigeria.

Omuemu and Olowe (2020) investigated the nexus between capital structure, agency cost and firm value among non-financial sector in Nigeria. Data was collected from 65 non- financial firms over the period from 2008 to 2018. Panel regression analysis was used and the analysis revealed that long term debt to assets and short term debt to assets being and indicator of capital structure has a positive and significant relationship with firm value. Also, the study found an inversely but insignificant relationship between debt to earnings before interest, taxes, depreciation, and amortization being a proxy of capital structure and the value of the firm.

Ifada et al. (2019) investigated the company attributes and firm value in companies listed on Jakarta Islamic index. SmartPLS program is used to analyze the data. They disclosed that ownership concentration and profitability have a positive effect on firm value. In contrast, liquidity has a negative effect on capital structure. However, this study did not discover any relationship between profitability and capital structure. Finally, capital structure mediates the relationship between profitability, liquidity and firm value.

Chaleeda et al. (2019) examined the effects of corporate financing decisions on firm value in Bursa Malaysia using sample of 256 firms from 9 sectors listed on Bursa Malaysia during the period 2000-2015. The study adopted Tobin's Q to representing firm value for the dependent variable. The corporate financing was measured by leverage (short-term debt to total assets, long-term debt to total assets, total debt to total assets and total debt to total equity) and debt maturity (long-term debt to total debt). Short-term debt to total assets and long-term debt to total assets has a positive significant relationship to firm value. They found that the total debt to total assets affects firm value negatively. This proves that although there are benefits of debts, there is also the cost of debts. The cost of debt financing arises from the increase in the probability of bankruptcy and firm value does not depend on the length of debt maturity.

Maneerattananungrot and Donkwa (2018) studied the capital structure affecting firm value in Thailand. They explored how performance, growth opportunity, tangible assets, risk, and liquidity affect a firm's capital structure and how capital structure affects firm value. Structural equation modeling was used to analyze financial data of 315 firms listed on the Stock Exchange of Thailand from 2012–2014. They found that tangibility positively affects debt financing and liquidity, risk negatively affects debt financing, and debt financing has no effect on a firm value. They suggested that financial managers could use these results to develop their capital structure to support other operations within the firm.

Ajibola, Wisdom and Qudus (2018) examined the impact of capital structure on financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria over the period 2005-2014.. The findings of the panel ordinary least square show that a positive statistically significant relationship exist between long term debt ratio, total debt ratio and return on equity while a positive statistically insignificant relationship between return on equity) and (Short term debt ratio). There was also a negative insignificant relationship between all the proxies of capital structure (LTD, STD and TD) and ROA which makes ROE a better measure of performance. regulators adopt measures that will promote leverage usage so as to maximize the overall value of the firm.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted expo-facto research design. This is because data needed for analysis already exist. The population of the study consisted 21 consumer goods companies listed by Nigerian Exchange Group. The purposive sampling technique was used to select (15) listed consumer goods companies between 2013 and 2022. The data collected for this study were obtained through the secondary source which were extracted from the audited annual financial reports and accounts of selected 15 Consumer-Goods companies in Nigeria. Descriptive and inferential statistics such as pane estimation techniques were used

Table 1: Summary of Measurement variables

Variables	Type of Variable	Variable Labels	Measurement	Expected Sign
Tobins q	Dependent	TOBQ	$\frac{\text{market value of equity} + \text{book value of debt}}{\text{Total assets}}$	
Long term debt	Independent	LTDE	Long -term debt /Equity	+
Short-term debt	Independent	STDE	Long -term debt/ Equity	+
Profitability Proxy by Return on Assets	Control	ROA	Profit After tax /Total assets	+

Source: Author's Computation (2024)

Model Specification

, the model adapted from work of (Chaleeda, *et al* 2019) was used and specified below based on functional and stochastic form as follows:

$$TOBQ = f(LTDE, STDE, ROA) \quad (1)$$

$$TOBQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LTDE_{it} + \beta_2 STDE_{it} + \beta_3 ROA + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Where:

TOBQ= Tobins q

STDE = Short term debt

LTDE= Long term debt

β_0 = Constant parameter

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Regression Coefficient of variables,

ε_{it} = Error terms

Note the subscription index "it"

t = time , i = company

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	TOBQ	LTDE	STDE	ROA
Mean	2.2807	0.1542	0.4132	0.0595
Median	1.5976	0.1460	0.3798	0.0528
Maximum	9.2873	0.5967	1.4975	0.2649
Minimum	0.3096	0.0069	0.0256	-0.3038
Std. Dev.	1.7635	0.1128	0.2029	0.0898
Skewness	1.7571	1.3059	2.1589	-0.6168
Kurtosis	6.0956	5.3554	12.892	5.2300
Jarque-Bera	137.082	77.3077	728.148	40.594
Probability	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
Sum	342.106	23.1322	61.9842	8.9179
Sum Sq. Dev.	463.361	1.8944	6.1326	1.2008
Observations	150	150	150	150

Source: Authors Computation, 2024

The result presented in Table.2 indicates that average tobins q was 1.2807 with minimum of 0.3096 and maximum of 9.2873. The average of both short term and long term debt stood at 41% and 15% respectively. These mean that the sampled firms used more of short term debt. The average return on asset is 5% ,the minimum and maximum values 26% and 30% respectively. This shows that the profitability of the sampled consumer goods firms was very poor and not encouraging. In addition, from Table 2 it was revealed that variable such as ROA was negatively skewed while others were positively skewed. The probabilities of Jarque-Bera of almost all the variables are less than 0.05, this implies that null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Matrix

	TBQ	LTDE	STDE	ROA	VIF
TBQ	1.0000				NA
LTDE	0.2459	1.0000			1.0511
STDE	-0.0480	-0.2183	1.0000		1.2557
ROA	0.3528	0.0608	-0.4075	1.0000	1.2003

Source: Authors Computation, 2024

Table 3 shows the results of the correlation among the variables. The results show that long term debt LTDE had positive and weak association with TOBQ given coefficient of 0.2459 respectively while STDE had negative and weak association with TOBQ with correlation coefficients of -0.0480 respectively. Similarly, the results indicate that return on assets had coefficients 0.3528. Other regressors have relatively weak relationship since their correlation coefficients are not up to 0.5. Hence, problem of multicollinearity did not occur. Therefore, there was no multicollinearity issue. Since the VIF values do not exceed the threshold of 10, the study's entire model is free of the multicollinearity issue.

Table 4 Regression Results

Dependent Variable: TOBQ

Method: Panel EGLS (Period random effects)

Date: 11/25/24 Time: 07:54

Variable	Coeff.	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.6008	0.4498	1.3357	0.1837
LTDE	3.9411	1.1883	3.3165	0.0012
STDE	1.4568	0.7249	2.0097	0.0463
ROA	7.9079	1.5951	4.9576	0.0000
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R-squared	0.3933	Mean dependent var		2.0092
Adjusted R-squared	0.3767	S.D. dependent var		1.7422
S.E. of regression	1.5808	Sum squared resid		364.826
F-statistic	11.663	Durbin-Watson stat		0.5115
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			
Heteros Test	7.6930		Prob. F(3,146)	0.0001
Serial Corre LM	69.8791		Prob. F(2,144)	0.0000
Hausman Test	2.8149		Prob.	0.4211

Source: Authors Computation, 2024

The Hausman Test's P-value of (0.4211) in Table 4 suggests that the Random effect is the most favoured. From the Table 4 , it was observed that the coefficient of determination for the regression as depicted by the R² value of 0.39 suggest that about 39 percent of the systematic variation of the dependent variable is accounted for by the explanatory variable while remaining 61% of the variation that is not explained . The F-statistics of 11.663 shows that the model of the study is well fitted; this can be confirmed by the

significant value of 0.000. This implies that there was significant relationship between financing decision and market value. Also, result of serial correlation of p- value 0.000 indicated existence of auto serial correlation in the data which is not significant at 5%. However, there was presence of heteroscedasticity in the study. Wald Test X^2 revealed the $p < 0.05$, which indicated all variables were parts of determinants factors of market value.

As depicted in Table 4, Long term debt had positive and significant effect on market value (t-val= 3.3165, $p < 0.05$). This implies that long-term debt allows companies to leverage their capital structure, potentially increasing returns on equity. If the company achieves returns on its investments that exceed the cost of long-term debt, this can positively influence the market value.

In addition, short term debt had positive and significant effect on market value (t-val= 2.0097, $p < 0.05$). This implies that short-term debt can help companies manage their liquidity needs effectively by providing quick access to cash for operational expenditures or to cover temporary cash shortfalls. This liquidity can enhance financial stability and investor confidence, positively impacting market value. Typically, short-term debt has lower interest rates compared to long-term debt. This can reduce financing costs in the short run, improving profitability and potentially increasing market value if the saved capital is reinvested wisely. On the side of control variable, return on assets had positive and significant effect on market value (t-val= 4.9576, $p < 0.05$). This implies that companies that demonstrate consistent profitability typically attract more investor interest. Steady earnings growth can lead to higher stock prices, as investors often look for companies that can generate sustainable returns over time

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study examines impact of debt financing decision on market value of listed consumer goods companies. The study disaggregated debt financing decision into long and short term. The study found that long term debt had positive and significant effect on market value. This means that companies often use debt to leverage their capital structure. This can amplify returns on equity when the company's investments generate returns that exceed the cost of debt, potentially increasing market value. Higher levels of debt increase financial risk. If a company fails to meet its debt obligations, it can lead to bankruptcy or financial distress, significantly impacting its market value. Investors may discount the company's stock price to reflect this higher risk. The way a company is perceived by investors can change based on its debt levels? A company that uses debt judiciously may be seen as aggressively pursuing growth, while excessive debt could lead to negative perceptions about management's capabilities and fiscal responsibility, potentially reducing market value. This finding supported by Adebayo, Olagunju and Ibrahim, 2022, Aggarwal and Padhan (2017); Ifada et al. (2019) but in contrary to outcome of Oladunjoye, et al., (2021). In addition, short term debt had positive and significant effect on market value. This demonstrated that short-term debt can provide flexibility and immediate liquidity benefits, it also carries risks related to cash flow volatility and refinancing. Short-term debt allows companies to seize opportunities quickly, such as purchasing inventory or funding urgent projects. This operational agility can lead to growth and improved market performance, enhancing company valuation. Profitability (return on assets) had positive and significant effect on market value. This implies that profitable companies generally have easier access to capital markets, as lenders and investors perceive them as less risky. This ability to raise funds can support further growth initiatives, enhancing future profitability and market value. This finding is consistent with Ifada et al. (2019)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that the effect of debt financing on the market value of a company is complex and depends on various factors, including the overall economic environment, interest rates on debt, and the company's specific circumstances. The study recommended that; though long-term debt financing is also carries risks that can influence market perception and company valuation. Thus, the management should manage debt levels wisely to optimize the company's market value. Companies must carefully manage

their short-term debt strategies to optimize the balance between accessibility to funds and maintaining investor confidence to sustain or enhance their market value

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